

Data Management Plan

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Executive Summary

The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide a document of reference regarding data and its management processes to be assured during Europe Startup Nations Alliance (ESNA) Project.

This version of the Data Management Plan is a preliminary deliverable that describes how the project is handling data (after 6 months of development).

The following updated versions of the DMP (M12 and M24) will ensure that procedures will be regularly updated, accordingly to the type of data to be managed, as the project progresses.

The document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement and its Annexes.

1. Introduction and Data Management Plan Overview

This document intends to specify the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Horizon Europe project “ESNA – Europe Startup Nations Alliance”.

The careful management of all project data and outputs is a key priority. Following the recent Guidelines on FAIR Data Management from EC, ESNA incorporates sound data management across the project life cycle and beyond.

This DMP follows the latest version of the Horizon Europe Data Management Template – giving a practical guidance on how data might be handled regarding each topic. It will be updated during the course of the project in order to follow **ESNA**’s 3 main objectives presented in *Picture 1*, and data involved in the planned activities of **the project** to achieve them.

<p>OBJECTIVE</p> <p>#1</p>	<p>Gather data from members and provide up to data key information on the ecosystem through a data driven open platform and analytics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Deploy a digital platform based on a shared common framework and bring the EU-27 onboard the new technology infrastructure ○ Develop and implement a strategy to obtain data on a regular basis ○ Provide real time data on the EU entrepreneurship ecosystem ○ Publish studies and thought leadership pieces
<p>OBJECTIVE</p> <p>#2</p>	<p>Improve National Policy Frameworks of Member States through monitoring of SNS adoption and best practice benchmarking, sharing and exchange</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Engage focal points in Member States and other stakeholders ○ Monitor and advise on SNS best practice adoption ○ Identify and develop best practices into deployable policies based on analysis of data gathered from members ○ Disseminate best practices through events, missions and staff-exchanges
<p>OBJECTIVE</p> <p>#3</p>	<p>Promote a proactive and open communication strategy on the European entrepreneurship agenda and policies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Strengthen high level EC sponsorship and institutionalize a strong European brand statement ○ Promote and contribute to EU policy agenda for entrepreneurship (5 years horizon) ○ Build awareness and eminence and encourage stronger relationships with ecosystems around the world

Picture 1 – ESNA’s main Objectives

Due to the content and planned activities to accomplish these goals, the Data management Plan aims to ensure that any data related to the project meets standards, legal requirements and the Grant Agreement requirements and conditions in all its stages.

Nevertheless, and depending on the data types, ESNA will apply specific procedures for the governance, technical, provenance, policy and legal requirements and related issues for all data processes in compliance with EU data protection legislation.

The Data Management Plan helps the project coordinator and person in charge of the data management to determine if the data involved in all the project processes and activities are properly controlled and monitored.

2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The gathering and analysis of member states data on their entrepreneurship systems and the provision of up-to-date key information on the EU ecosystem as a whole through an Open Digital Platform is at the core of **ESNA**'s mission.

The project is still at an early stage of development, and therefore, no data is being used, and type and volume of data is still under evaluation. Hence, this will be a topic to discuss in the following stages of the project as well as the Open Digital Platform will be developed:

- In some activities, it is intended to gather data from members and provide up to data key information on the ecosystem through a data driven open platform and analytics.
- For all data outputs, DMP will specify types and their estimated size (e.g., text, image, audio, source code) including large size data.

To ensure the accessibility of ESNA data analysis and reports beyond the end of the project, digital datasets and the project website will be integrated into the Horizon Results Platform Single Electronic Data Interchange Area (SEDIA) or other EU-owned online hubs, such as EU Academy or EOOSC.

Aligned with the definitions written in the deliverable '*Quality Project Management*' special attention will be given in order to control and monitor the access and exchange of data resulting from the deliverables resulting from ESNA and other documentation to be stored and accessed under the directory tree structured, regarding the Delivery process for project outcomes as well from External communication, Publications and Presentations of project results.

3. FAIR data¹

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

These questions will be discussed in the following stages of the platform and project development in order to define processes for the **findability** (devise solutions for the use of trusted repositories during and beyond the project), how data will be identified, and which metadata's standards needs to be followed.

¹ FAIR data - Data which meet principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability

3.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Since the project is at an early-stage, appropriate arrangements will be explored in the following months to identify the repository or storage solutions where the data will be deposited.

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Regarding the availability or the access to the data related to the project and/or the platform itself, **further information will be provided in the following versions of the DMP.**

To specify **accessibility** modes, IPR considerations and the exploitation of results concerning data will be included, open access considerations (including timeline of public data access/publication and when accounting for embargo periods), provisions for access to restricted data for verification purposes and regular backups, rules for data use and collaborative generation of datasets among members, e-infrastructures to store all data collected, used, or generated in the project.

Regarding **Open science practices**, ESNA will promote an open, cooperative work and a systematic sharing of knowledge on national entrepreneurial ecosystems and its impacts throughout the whole process. As part of this process and within the specifications and deployment of the Open Platform (outside the scope of the present project) it will implement discoverable, accessible, reusable and transparent open science practice including for the open sharing of data amongst all its registered members, data management and management of data outputs (see below) and wide dissemination of the most relevant outcomes. Open Access (OA) will be applied:

- i) to conference outputs (including posters, abstracts, slideshows) such as the Web Summit in Lisbon, EU-Startups Summit, SLUSH, Invest Europe – Investors’ Forum, Futures Conference, Living Knowledge, with the aim to outreach a minimum of 10.000 innovators and *startupp*ers at these events, as well as national policy-makers, ecosystem actors, citizens, civil society and end users in the co-creation of entrepreneurship agendas and contents;
- ii) to reports on the ESNA Digital Platform, as well as the one published in online repository and portals (e.g., Zenodo, OpenAIRE, OpenDOAR, GitHub) under the CC-BY Creative Commons attribution license, i.e., copyrights are retained by ESNA, while the access and the download are allowed to any users. The shared digital infrastructure will feed the European Data Infrastructure (EDI) and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC);
- iii) to grey literature and bibliographic metadata that will be deposited in Digital Platform and disseminated through the digital channels of the project (website, social media).

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

The project is at an early stage, and therefore, no data or metadata is currently available.

3.3 Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references² to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Non applicable at this stage of the project. However, in the following months, it is intended to define modes for the **interoperability**: standards, formats, lexicon for data and metadata (e.g., metadata-complete attribute and semantic data enrichment). The structure of the data packages and links between different datasets will be carefully defined due to the variability of data outcomes.

3.4 Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

Regarding **multiple modes for the reusability**, the DMP will define licenses for data sharing and re-use from ESNA members (e.g., Creative Commons, Open Data Commons, availability of tools/software/models for data generation and validation/interpretation /re-use).

4. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles

Non applicable at this stage, but compliance with the FAIR principles will be managed.

² A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

5. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Further steps will be carried out in the next months to decide on how data will be kept and for how long, as well the person/team responsible for data management, digital curation, and quality assurance, preservation requirements and expected costs over the medium and long term.

6. Data Security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Data will be safely stored in trusted repositories. Is intended to plan the timings to back up, tools and recovery procedures.

7. Ethics

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

It's not expected any ethics or legal issues with an impact on data sharing. It's not expected the access of/to personal data, but in case of data sharing and long-term preservation concerning this matter, an informed consent will be defined and included in proper procedures.

8. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

At this early stage of the project, no other issues are expected that require the need of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.